

WAYS TO IMPROVE THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE ENGINEERS

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Abstract: *Improving the professional competence of future engineers requires a holistic approach that incorporates technical skills, soft skills, real-world experience, and personal and professional development. Engaging in a combination of these initiatives can help to equip engineers with the tools and knowledge they need to succeed in their chosen profession.*

Keywords: *competence, pedagogical mechanisms, professional mentoring, cooperative education, mastered education, projects.*

Pedagogy refers to the study of teaching and learning processes, methods, and strategies. It is concerned with the various approaches and methods that can be used to teach students and facilitate their learning. The goal of pedagogy is to enhance the effectiveness of teaching and learning and to provide a better understanding of how people learn.

Pedagogy involves both theory and practice and encompasses a wide range of disciplines such as psychology, education, and sociology. It focuses on the process of teaching and learning and aims to develop effective teaching strategies that can improve student learning outcomes. Some key features of pedagogy include:

1. Personalization: Learning needs to be personalized to meet the individual needs of each student.
2. Active learning: Active participation and engagement of students in the learning process is critical to their overall success.

3. Critical thinking: Critical thinking skills are essential for students to be able to identify and solve problems, analyze and interpret information, and make informed decisions.

4. Collaborative Learning: Collaborative learning involves working together in groups to share ideas and knowledge, and to develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter.

5. Feedback: Regular feedback and assessment are important to monitor student progress and adjust teaching approaches as needed.

In strengthening initial education, it is essential to focus on pedagogy as a means of enhancing the effectiveness of teaching and learning. This can be achieved through a range of strategies including the use of technology, collaborative learning, and active and student-centered approaches to teaching. It is also important to ensure that teachers are trained in the latest pedagogical approaches and have the necessary skills to effectively apply them in their teaching practice [1].

Practicals: Pedagogy is the study of teaching and learning methods applied in education. It involves the analysis of the various methods, tools, techniques, and strategies used in teaching, and their effectiveness in improving learning outcomes. Pedagogy is an interdisciplinary field that draws its concepts and principles from psychology, sociology, philosophy, and education.

Practical training in pedagogy refers to the application of the theoretical concepts and principles learned in the classroom to actual classroom situations. Here is some complete information about practical training in pedagogy:

1. Goals of practical training: Practical training in pedagogy aims to equip students with the skills, knowledge, and competencies required to effectively plan, deliver, and evaluate teaching and learning processes. It provides students with hands-on experience in designing lesson plans, delivering lectures, managing students, using instructional technology, and assessing learning outcomes.

2. Methods of practical training: Practical training in pedagogy can be achieved through various methods such as classroom teaching, field observations, internships, and practicum experiences. These methods provide students with opportunities to observe and practice different teaching strategies and techniques in real classrooms, under the guidance of experienced teachers.

3. Evaluation of practical training: Practical training in pedagogy is evaluated through grading systems that assess the student's ability to apply theoretical concepts and principles to real classroom situations. The evaluation may include performance assessments, written assignments, exams, and reflective journals.

4. Benefits of practical training: Practical training in pedagogy helps students to develop critical thinking skills, creativity, problem-solving skills, and effective communication skills. It also provides students with a realistic understanding of the challenges and demands of teaching and prepares them for a professional career in the education field.

5. Availability of practical training: Practical training in pedagogy is available at all levels of education, from elementary to postgraduate programs. It is offered by colleges and universities, as well as by teacher training institutes, and professional organizations. Online platforms are also available that offer practical training in pedagogy in a virtual classroom setting.

In conclusion, practical training in pedagogy is an essential component of teacher education. It provides students with the necessary skills, knowledge, and experience to become effective teachers and positively impact the learning outcomes of their students.

Analytical work and project work: In pedagogy, analytical work, and project work are two different approaches to teaching and learning. Analytical work involves breaking down a subject into smaller parts and analyzing each one in detail. It is a process of examining and understanding something by studying its various components and identifying relationships between them. The focus of

analytical work is to develop critical thinking skills and to deepen students' understanding of a subject.

On the other hand, project work is a collaborative and experiential approach to learning. It involves designing and carrying out a project that requires students to apply the knowledge and skills they have learned in a particular subject. Project work involves identifying a problem or issue, conducting research, devising solutions, and presenting the findings to an audience. The focus of project work is on active learning, creativity, and problem-solving.

Both analytical work and project work are important approaches in pedagogy, and they can be used in combination to enhance students' understanding of a subject. Analytical work can provide the foundation for a project, while project work can provide a context for applying and refining analytical skills. By combining these approaches, teachers can create a more dynamic and engaging learning environment that promotes critical thinking, creativity, and real-world problem-solving skills.

In conclusion, Pedagogy is a dynamic field that is constantly evolving. As technology advances and new learning research emerges, pedagogical practices must adapt to keep pace. For this reason, pedagogy is a crucial area of study for anyone interested in education or teaching. This helps to train them to acquire the necessary skills for faster professional development and to perform useful tasks for the public. Also, the voluntariness of each student is very important in the process of improving pedagogical mechanisms. There was a need for students to research and provide feedback on career-oriented tasks. All of the pedagogical mechanisms presented here are very useful for developing the professional competence of future engineers. Therefore, do them correctly and remember that you need to provide special education for each student.

References:

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